

A Women in Crop Science Conversation with.....Josie Clarke

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Background & spotlight on Ability Agriculture

Our Women in Crop Science community interview series aims to learn and share stories from women who are part of our community. The interview format developed by Julie Van Vlasselaer captures both professional and personal activities and motivations. I was keen to include Josie Clarke in our conversation series when I learnt about her initiative Ability Agriculture during her recent research exchange to CIMMYT. She has developed and launched this alongside her day job as a PhD student in crop improvement at The University of Sydney. Ability Agriculture is a pioneering initiative to achieve greater awareness and inclusion for disabled people in agriculture. This is urgently needed with statistics released ahead of the 2021 International Day of People with Disability revealing that 76% of those with a disability who are employed are not willing to disclose that they have a disability.

For Josie, this indicates that there is a fear of disclosing the need for extra support in the workplace and a feeling that if you have a disability, whether it be physical, non-physical, visible, or invisible that this impacts your chance of getting, or keeping, a job. Josie was motivated to change this to achieve greater transparency in our workplaces through support for accessible roles and raising awareness of disability in our workplaces.

This led to the founding of Ability Agriculture, an Australia-based initiative developed and led by Josie. The initiative is

opening the conversation and giving a voice to highlight that agriculture can be an accessible career option for disabled people. Josie's vision is that this will showcase the diversity of roles and career pathways

available in agriculture that are accessible, as well as allowing the sector to build a more diverse and flexible work force for the future. This will ultimately support and promote the growth and sustainability of rural communities.

Ability Agriculture shares stories via www.abilityagriculture.com, as well as through Instagram and Facebook (Ability_Agriculture). These highlight examples of personal resilience but also showcase the incredible career pathways available in agriculture to those with disability. Josie hopes that sharing stories will bring greater transparency for accessible development programs and will inspire young people with disabilities into careers in agriculture.

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Briefly describe what you do?

I'm a second year PhD student at The University of Sydney in Australia investigating the application of gene editing for sustainable crop improvement. The focus of my research is on nitrogen use efficiency and chloride tolerance (both major challenges to cereal production in Australian agriculture).

Why did you get into research, and crop science in particular?

I've always had a passion for agriculture. My family are generational beef farmers with experience in growing corn and soybean on the mid north coast of Australia. I have always loved genetics and did work experience in a cytogenetics ward at a leading hospital a few months before following the pathway in agriculture. Contributing to crop improvement, and to the role that gene editing can play for improvement in cultivars is essential as it continues to become more and more challenges to meet global crop production needs. Being able to see the direct benefit of our research to growers is something that makes working in agriculture so exciting and rewarding for me.

Lab or field? Porque no los dos – definitely both.

Conference or stakeholder meeting? Stakeholder meeting – hearing what growers want and need and having them in the decision making process is so important to ensure we are focusing research outcomes with an industry and community focus.

Literature review or project report? Lit review – or even better opinion article – asking where we are going next and identifying our faults and triumphs to take with us into the next stage.

Conventional or molecular methods? Molecular – that will supplement the necessity of conventional breeding, there's so much potential, reduced timeframes and great benefits.

Hybrid, inbred or vegetative? Hybrids – you can't beat hybrid vigour.

Qualitative or quantitative research? Again both – they both tell a story, the challenge of taking a qualitative trait and turning into a quantitative measure or marker is exciting.

Genstat or R? Genstat – PRISM for making graphs though, I've had one too many miss placed symbol experiences in R.

Favorite crop & why? Very hard to choose! As an Australian I could say barley because it's the key ingredient in beer. But for colour, canola, and soybean because it reminds me of home.

What do you love most about your job?

Problem solving and communicating with others for collaborative problem solving – as well as being challenged and pushed out of my comfort zone, I always feel like im learning and progressing

Any major hurdles?

Learning to ask for help, definitely as a PhD student you may sometimes feel like a burden but being able to ask for help and also learn from others and take advice has helped so much: “there’s no such thing as a stupid question!”

What is your dream to achieve in your field of expertise?

For me I’d love to be involved in commercial research or an industry research group. I would always love to come back to academia and bring that knowledge from the industry back. In my experience I’ve always learnt the most from academics with commercial experience.

Who has influenced you most and why?

Gosh, a lot of people. From having great mentors in horticulture who encouraged me to follow my dream because they knew I liked research. My honours mentor Helen Bramley who supported me and again helped me follow my dream of doing me PhD and let me explore my own topics (I love epigenetics and the potential of epigenetic priming as a short-term solutions for cultivar improvement for events such as drought and heat stress).

Most important publication or the publication of which you are most proud?

Funnily enough, I’m just about to submit my first one – whichever one it is I’ll be probably frame it on my wall.

What is your favorite aspect of your research?

Getting to be hands on, learning new methods and thinking of ways of making old methods more efficient.

What would make your research and crop science experience even better?

The opportunity to collaborate and do even more work experience at other institutions. There’s so much to learn from other scientists and institutions. I really enjoyed my time at CIMMYT, not just from the technical aspect, but from meeting other professionals and listening to their career journeys.

What is the best career decision you ever made and why?

Leaving – it doesn’t sound great but leaving my role as an agronomist to pursue my PhD. Leaving is never an easy thing to do, you may feel like your letting others down, but taking the risk and following what is best for your potential is something I am proud of. I’m especially proud of it because it wasn’t an easy thing to do.

Where do you see yourself in 5 years?

In 5 years I hope to have my own contract research consultancy firm, leasing or owning a farm and growing crops with my family. In the next 6 months I will have launched my not-for-profit and charity

Ability Agriculture in order to increase awareness, representation and opportunity for those with disabilities in agriculture.

Beach or mountain? Ahhh both – my family’s farm is surrounded by Mount Yarahappini, but we are also only 20 minutes from the beach, so I’ve grown up loving “up river and down river” as we call it in my home town.

Tea or coffee? Chai latte.

Appetizer or dessert? Dessert.

Instagram or Twitter? Insta.

Fame or fortune? Fortune.

Final word

Josie is an incredibly inspiring member of our community: combining her love of applied research to improve crops with advocacy and passion for achieving greater inclusion in agriculture. She aspires to see more voices at the table: all the way from access to employment and support through to policy change and workforce planning. There are huge opportunities to do more, in Australia, as well as globally. Josie is currently launching Ability Agriculture as a not-for-profit charity and will start the Ability Agriculture Fund. She hopes to create scholarships for advocates and to support those with disability to study and participate in industry leadership programs, and to attend and champion inclusion of disabled voices at major agricultural events and rural conferences. She also wants to create a job site as a single-entry point for information on accessible roles in rural Australia.

I wasn’t aware that the employment rate for those with disability (physical, non-physical, visible, and invisible) has not changed in Australia in over 30 years. Josie, and Ability Agriculture, aim to change this for agriculture and rural Australia through raising awareness, providing transparency, and providing information on accessible roles. This will be a great step towards building the sustainability of rural communities, creating, and supporting diverse and inclusive workforces. There are definitely big things to come for Ability Agriculture. Congratulations Josie and thank you for your inspiring leadership in supporting greater inclusion and diversity in the agricultural sector.

More about Ability Agriculture

Ability Agriculture is currently looking for Expressions of Interest for Board members. If you would like to help Ability Agriculture, please get in touch info@abilityagriculture.com

You can read more about the work of Ability Agriculture in these recent articles:

- <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2021-02-27/ability-agriculture-proves-winning-formula/13188410>
- <https://thefarmermagazine.com.au/ability-agriculture-changing-the-dreams-of-many-farmers/>

You can also watch recent videos about Ability Agriculture here:

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-N7jNnrjnSw&t=3s>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=479T6nM0QiQ>